

LA-CoNGA Physics perspectives for the Latin America Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure (v1.0)

Thematic areas

- Capacity Building and Education
- Experimental High Energy Physics
- Instrumentation and Computing

Abstract

This note summarizes the activities and the scientific and technical perspectives of the Latin American Alliance for Capacity building in Advanced Physics (LA-CoNGA Physics) community: <https://laconga.redclara.net>. First, the LA-CoNGA Physics project is introduced and then we advocate for the development of additional capacity building activities within the community to further strengthen the different efforts in High Energy Physics, AstroParticles and Cosmology in the Latin American region.

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¹ Not all members of the project in the different universities were added in the list, just the representatives. Please contact us if you are interested in the full list..

Scientific context: Global problems, global science and a global community

The past hundred years have seen giant leaps forward in our understanding of both the macroscopic and microscopic universe. Nevertheless many unknowns remain, e.g. the inexplicably large baryon asymmetry of the universe, the unexplained nature of dark matter (DM) and dark energy, and the unknown relationship between quantum mechanics and gravity. Together they are a clear indication of particles and forces beyond our current understanding, and motivate the continued search for more complete theories of nature at both the very large and very small scales and the construction of new research infrastructure needed for those searches.

Capacity building programs and the modernisation of the educational platforms in Latin-America will be key in order to form the new generation of scientists and engineers that will profit and work with these new research infrastructures. Capacity building programs will be particularly important to include in this ambitious enterprise institutions in the region with episodic funding and subcritical mass in High Energy Physics (HEP)-trained human resources as they cannot compete with the opportunities of large research universities, which used latest digital education tools and are closely linked to hands-on experimental facilities and a network of companies. Ideally the output of these programs will be the creation and/or strengthening of Virtual Research and Learning Communities (VRLC) including all these academic institutions, as well as industrial partners, adding up the corresponding local resource and infrastructures to attain critical mass and share expertise.

LA-CoNGA Physics: objectives, methodology, list of participant institutions, current status, timelines and challenges

LA-CoNGA Physics is an innovative proposal to modernize the educational strategy in eight universities in Colombia, Ecuador, Peru and Venezuela. LA-CoNGA Physics will implement a cross-institutional Master's degree in HEP based on a modern e-learning platform, with open-access tools to interconnect a problem-solving-oriented curriculum with instrumentation laboratories and internships in leading research centers and industrial partners, both in Latin America and Europe. LA-CoNGA Physics is funded under the frame of the Erasmus+ Programme, the European Framework Programme dedicated to education, and is scheduled to start in January 2020 for a period of three years.

In the current information age, higher education is becoming globally distributed and inseparable from actual research and development in enterprises and companies VRLCs have proven to be an effective scheme due to their possibilities for multi-institutional participation, synchronous and asynchronous online engagement, decentralised student discussion, academic networking, and cost-effectiveness. This type of cooperative lecturing arrangements exposes students and academic staff to a variety of cutting-edge concepts and techniques that cannot be accessed from just using standard textbooks.

The specific goals that derive from the project are:

- Support the modernization, accessibility to knowledge and internationalisation of higher education in the partner institutions based on the integrations, installation, and training for

innovative e-learning platform and open-access tools (Softwares, contents and Data). As well as the installation of instrumentation laboratories for the courses.

- Strengthen inter-institutional relations among partner institutions and with partner institutions in Europe and larger/established institutions in Latin-America through interactions within the virtual research and learning community, including internships at the institutes in Latin America and in the EU.
- Promote convergence in the curricular offering in HEP in the universities and close cooperation in academic activities trying to match the EU Bologna model. Such convergence could facilitate the exchange of students among the various countries.

LA-CoNGA Physics builds on the activities of the CEVALE2VE (Centro Virtual de Altos Estudios de Altas Energías in Spanish) group. After four versions of the virtual graduate course 'Introduction to Particle Physics' with six universities in Colombia, Peru and Venezuela participating since 2016 CEVALE2VE has gathered enough experience to expand and successfully tackle LA-CoNGA Physics. The following research and industrial institutions participate in LA-CoNGA Physics as Associated Partners: 4 world-recognized international research centers, 2 non-for-profit organizations and 3 private companies. In parenthesis the scientific/industrial contacts for the associated partners.

- CERN, European Organization for Nuclear Research, Switzerland (Salvatore Mele)
- DESY, Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron, Germany (James Ferrando and Sergio Diez Cornell)
- ICTP, Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Italy (Bobby Acharya and Arturo Sanchez)
- IRFU, Institut de Recherche sur les lois Fondamentales de l'Univers, France (Bruno Lenzi)
- RedCLARA, Cooperación Latinoamericana de Redes Avanzadas, Uruguay (Luis Eliecer Cadenas)
- NYAS, New York Academy of Sciences, USA (Alejandro de la Puente)
- ACAC, Asociación Colombiana para el Avance de la Ciencia, Colombia (Diego Chavarro)
- CAEN, Costruzioni Apparecchiature Elettroniche Nucleari, Italy
- FrontierX Analytics, Colombia (Raul Ramos Pollán)
- DBaccess, Perú (Angelo Burgazzi)
- Camila Rangel, from The Turing Institute, UK

The first year of LA-CoNGA Physics will be devoted to preparation: syllabus of the one-year master program, installation of the teaching instrumentation labs in the partner universities and the development of the e-learning platform. The first year of master will start in January 2021 and a second edition will run during 2022 (implementing all the lessons learned during the first edition). The project faces challenges associated to the preparation phase in each country and the sustainability of the project after 2023. Redundancy in the know-how of the participating groups ensures smooth continuity in the activity and additional training measures of local personpower will be implemented to mitigate the risks.

Perspectives for future activities

In the short-timescale LA-CoNGA Physics will run for a period of 3 years, starting in 2020. We look forward to working together with other institutions participating in LASF4RI to ensure the sustainable continuation of the masters in HEP in all the partner institutions (and others that want to join in the future) and that participating institutions become officially involved in large HEP projects discussed within LASF4RI.

Within LA-CoNGA Physics there are several ways to get involved: in the courses, in the schools and workshops being planned. Having other institutions in the region and from other fields use the e-learnings and build their own VRLCs will also ensure that the impact of the project will be sustained beyond its lifetime.

Capacity building projects like LA-CoNGA Physics will have a positive impact in the field in helping local programs to keep going while preparing to rebuild capabilities in the future, so they must be part of a global effort to ensure our involvement in the next generation experiments in the fields of Particle Physics, Astroparticles and Cosmology and in what are likely to be profound and exciting discoveries.